

THE CHURCH IN POLITICS FOR GOOD GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIAN SOCIETY

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Abstract

The church is a political entity. Within itself, politics is carried out. The relationship between the church and politics continues unabated in political philosophy. The term “Church” is “ekklesia”, meaning the called-out ones. In the Greek language, the word is used almost exclusively for political gatherings. In the course of the findings, the researcher found out that the church of God in Nigerian nation state, have succeeded in many aspects both within and outside the country but in the area of politics, could not due to several reasons such as lack of involvement in partisan politics, ethical challenges and corruption, religious and ethnic tensions, ineffective advocacy for social justice, lack of ethical leadership, inadequate civil engagement among others. It is in view of the above that the study aims to unearth the active involvement of the church in partisan politics in Nigeria. The paper seeks the historical context of the church's participation in politics from the colonial era to post independence, pointing out both the moral and theological motivations. The paper equally examines the current political landscape, identifying the representation of the church in major political parties cum the various challenges encountered, such as corruption, electoral malpractices, complex a political arena, a hostile nature and religious crises in our nation state. The study further examines the vital contributions of the church in good governance through advocacy for justice, ethical leadership, as well as community development initiatives. In a nutshell, the work concludes by making the following recommendations, such as ethical training for Nigerian Christian politicians, promotion of inter-faith dialogue, fostering civil education and strengthening accountability mechanisms. Above all, the study underscores the potential of the church's involvement in Nigerian politics with the sole intention

to significantly improve good governance in contemporary Nigeria, provided that ethical and civil principles are upheld. The study uses a combination of socio-historical cum interactive methods of enquiry in the gathering of facts.

KEYWORDS: Church Involvement, Politics, Good Governance.

Introduction:

The involvement of Christians in political activities dates back to the colonial era, where education, health care and social services were influenced by the Christian missionaries. Consequent upon the above contributions, a foundation was laid for Christian involvement in political activities.

The active engagement of Christians in Nigerian politics is often driven by a sense of moral responsibility with the sole intention to promote justice, equity as well and the common good. In Nigeria as a nation state, different perspectives have been offered by the various denominations on political engagement, ranging from active participation to more cautious approaches to avoid compromising religious values. The above differences notwithstanding, various denominations in our nation state shared ethical teachings of Christianity, such as integrity, service and the pursuit of justice, which can significantly influence political structure and governance practices.

In a nutshell, that the church should remain aloof from politics is impossible because the church itself is a political institution that creates position for people that has particular interests. If we accept the fact that the church does indeed have both pragmatic and theological reasons for getting involved in politics, another question arises: what should be the nature of involvement? How should the church, as well as individual Christians, relate to society in matters of politics? Experience has shown that the above questions are difficult to answer, and that is why the work is aimed at addressing them.

Clarification of Concepts

Church

The word church came from a Greek word “ekklesia” meaning “an assembly”. It came from the word kaleo, meaning “accompany” (Luke 9:11), while ek implies “out of” that is, “an assembly of the called ones”, and that is where we got the chosen ones in the New Testament or the elect. The term church has three implications, first and foremost, it means the people of God throughout the ages, that is, from the beginning of the creation to date, which includes the existing people before the creation of the Jews. Secondly, it also implies, in a narrow sense, a visible gathering of people. In a more restricted sense, it means believers in Christ according to 1 Corinthians 10:32, Galatians 1:13 (Abalaka, 2022).

The word which Jesus used and has been translated “church” meant originally a collection of people meeting, gathering or a community. It was the word used for the Old Testament community, the Christians that came into being on the day of Pentecost (Exo 12:13, 6:35, Deut 9:10, 23:3, Matt 18:18, Acts 5:11, 7:38, 8:11, 26). When one is speaking of the church, there are at least three polarities which must be kept in mind. First, the church is both the whole body of Christ (Catholic, Protestant, Anglican, Orthodox and Oriental and a particular denomination or community within it. Secondly, the church is both the whole body of God (laity, religious and clergy alike) and particularly groups within it (e.g the hierarchy or the official church). Thirdly, the church is both the universal and local church. Indeed, the universal church is the collection of local churches.

As the head has absolute control over the body, so Christ has supreme authority over the church (Eph 1:22-23). On the other hand, as the body shares in the life of the head, so the church shares in the life of the risen Christ. It is united in Him in His victory over death and all the evil spiritual forces of the universe (Matt 18:18, Eph 1:21, 2:5-7, 3:10-21). In view of the above, Flemming (2004) notes that if the picture of the body emphasises the life, unity and growth that Christ gives to the church, the picture of marriage emphasises the love that Christ has for the Church. That love was so great that to gain the Church as His bride, Christ laid His life in view of the Church in all its perfection as the body of Christ, is one world of sin and failure (1 Corin 3: 1-3). God sees the church as the total number of believers in all nations in all eras-a vast, ongoing, international community commonly referred to as the church universally. While some see it only in the form of those believers who are living in a particular place at a particular time.

The church is defined as the prophetic appearance of the kingdom. Two ideas flow from the definition: (i). The church is related to the kingdom ii, but the church is not equal to the kingdom of God. The historical Jesus founded or organised the church. Not until after the resurrection that the New Testament speak with regularity about the church. However, there is an adumbration of the church in the teaching and ministry of Jesus, in both general and specific ways. In general, Jesus anticipated the later official formation of the church in that He gathered to Himself twelve disciples who constituted the beginning of eschatological Israel, in effect, the remnant. More specifically, Jesus explicitly referred to the church in two passages: Matt 16:18-19 and 18:17. In the first passage, Jesus promised that He would build His church despite satanic opposition, thus assuring the ultimate success of His mission. The notion of the church overcoming the forces of evil coincides with the idea that the kingdom of God will prevail over its enemies. The second passage relates to the future organisation of the church, particularly its method of discipline, not unlike the Jewish synagogue practices of Jesus' day (Abalaka, 2022).

He concluded that the New Testament identifies the church as the people of the kingdom itself. Moreover, the church is an instrument of the kingdom. This is especially clear from Matthew 16 18-19, where the preaching of Peter and the church becomes the keys to opening up the kingdom to all who would enter. From the foregoing, we could speak of the church as a timeless and universal community; more commonly, it speaks of it as a group of Christians meeting together in a particular locality.

Involvement

The church and every Christian should be active in the world. The church as the body cannot remain aloof from political life if it is accepted that the word is intended not simply for the individual but also for the community. This should be openly admitted instead of pretending neutrality and shunning involvement in a delicate issue (Kunhiyop, 2008). Jom Taylor in Kunhiyop (2008), speaks in view of the above issue:

The church must be rooted in the society within which it has grown up. Its members are a part of that society, sharing its traditional points of view, influenced by its history and involved in its strength and its weakness, its rise or fall. A church which is cut off from the rest of society, living a separate, endorsed life of its own, will be ineffective and will probably, in the end, become paralysed or perish altogether.

Politics

According to Richard (2009), asserts that when one is speaking of politics, there are at least two meanings at hand: the classical and practical. Politics may refer to the affairs of “the city” (the polis) Richard insisted that a political community arises from argument and dialogue among its members, especially regarding justice and the ground of that unity which is called peace”. If the public argument dies from disinterest or subsides into the angry mutterings of polemic, or trails off or get lost in positivistic triviality or get lost in a morass of semantics”, he declared “you may be sure of that the barbarian is at the gates of the city” In a nutshell, Richard further opines that more practical meaning of politics links it with the process by which power to achieve justice and peace is conferred and exercised.

Benson (2019) added to the above, as he notes that politics involves critical and systematic analysis of political life and the activity of government. He further asserts that it plays the roles of adaptation, integration, allocation of human and material resources, resolution of conflicts and promoting much understanding and co-operation. He concluded that politics can be understood as an implicit and

explicit organisation of society for human good, which entails active and dynamic participation of an eligible citizen.

Governance is the process of decision-making and the process by which decisions are implemented or not implemented. UNESCAP in Agenyi and Johnson (2022) asserted that since governance is the process of decision-making and the process by which decisions are implemented, an analysis of governance focuses on the formal and informal actors involved in decision-making. The above writers added that the government is one of the actors involved in governance. According to the above writers, other actors involved in governance vary depending on the level of government that is under discussion.

Furthermore, the above writers concluded that good governance is the process of measuring how public institutions conduct public affairs and manage public resources and guarantee the realisation of human rights in a manner essentially free of abuse and corruption with due regard for the rule of law. Mohit (2013) lays credence to the above as he opines that good governance implies mobilising the people of the country in the best direction possible. He concluded that good governance requires the unity of people in society and motivates them to attain political objectivity. It also ensures the power utilisation of all the resources of the state for the citizens, which ensures sustainable development.

Reasons for the non-participation of the church in politics

In view of the non-participation of the church in active politics, to many Christians, anything besides preaching and teaching the word of God is a distraction from the mission of the gospel. Odudele Rotimi and Isaac Olusola (2023) lay credence to the above as they assert that many committed Christians are hardly encouraged to take part in politics because it has been a convention to regard partisan politics as a dirty game and therefore unfit for a committed Christian.

In an interview with Ajeka at Abocho in Dekina local government area of Kogi state (2025), he was of the same view as the above writers that “the involvement of the church in partisan politics is an impediment to one’s stand in the Lord” he added that politics is a dirty game as well as unhygienic to the church of God. He further notes that a committed Christian cannot involve himself in politics for reasons that a greater number of politicians do not put God first. That since politics has become or die affair, the greater majority of them go diabolical, sacrificing human beings to win at all costs. It is in view of the above that this paper aims at addressing the nature of involvement of the church in Nigerian politics, most especially that preaching and teaching the gospel message in the church is not adequate to change the societal vices.

Many committed Christians in Nigeria think that they could not agree with some of the things the party stands for. Several of these Christians would have no problem accepting political office, provided it comes by appointment. To them, political appointees in Nigeria generally serve the interests of the one who made the appointments. Many of what the party stand for are against the teachings and tenets of Christianity (Odudele and Olusola, 2023). The researcher lays credence in the above as he affirms that in Igala land of Kogi state, Nigeria, politicians had deviated from the party norms because of selfish interest and any attempt to correct such ills amounts to the hiring of political thugs to assassinate.

In view of the above, Olusola and Odudele (2023) conclude that it is completely absurd for a Christian leader to claim to be patriotic by merely encouraging his members to participate in voting while discouraging them from political party membership. The implication, according to them, is that a Christian politician must agree and learn the dynamics of what the party stands for to plan, pray and execute political ideologies.

Added to the above, it is usually said that power corrupts and absolute power corrupts absolutely. Thus, power corrupts and leads to anarchy and bloodshed.

According to the above writers, many people who seek political office do so because there is power in politics, and the corrupt always seek power.

They added that the majority of the Christians interviewed say that there is money in politics and this has become an attraction for those desirous of riches. To them, politicians are selfish and self-centred. They oppressed, exploited, deceived, and subjugated the common people who voted them in during the election. The above authors concluded that other corrupt practices of the politicians in our contemporary society include that campaigns can get nasty as so much dust gets thrown around, and stealing from those who want to get the reins of power at all costs.

In view of the above, the researcher, in an interview with a Christian leader at Elika in Dekina LGA, Kogi state, one Mr Gabriel, lays credence to the above that involvement of Christians in politics has adverse effects on one's standing in the Lord because of the corrupt practices in politics in the Nigerian society. He added that in our nation state, elections is no longer free and fair, vote buying, election rigging, snatching of ballot boxes, hiring of political thugs have become the order of the day. He concluded that Judges, INEC officials, as well as law enforcement agencies in our nation state (Nigeria), have been bought over to manipulate election results, and as such, he strongly advised Christians not to participate in politics. However, in view of what Christ states about Christians standing as light of the world, Christians should not hesitate in answering political calls to create a political impact that would be of great benefit to the country at large.

There are various misconceptions of the biblical text on what politics is. As a result, many church clerics and church organisations discourage their members from participating in politics. It is a known fact that some Christian denominations in Nigeria have even taken measures to suspend or excommunicate their members or clerics who ventured into politics. One can understand the fears of such denominations, given the antecedents of Christians in other countries (Odule and Olusola, 2023). In an interview (2025) with a cleric in the United Evangelical Church Erika in Igalaland, it was revealed that a cleric was suspended for some years for supporting a political party and attending a political rally. The above shows a misconception of what politics is. Interested and committed Christians should not hesitate to join politics, but to be there as salt and light of the world.

The Nature of the Church Involvement

Involvement in politics is not without risks, and therefore, some caution is also in order. One of the important roles the church ought to play in politics is that of the custodian and exponent of truth. The church must stand on the truth and advocate for adherence to the truth and social justice. (Gaya in Abalaka (2016)) affirms that the church cannot perform the first role effectively until it serves as the custodian of truth. Abalaka equally notes that the question that arises is how the church becomes the custodian of truth. The answer is when it doesn't see what is wrong, either by commission or by omission. Secondly, it will be the custodian of truth if it does not become partisan. The effect, according to him, is that if it does that, it can break the Church. Thirdly, the church is to expand truth from the Bible without fear or favour.

In view of the above, what is now the position of the church? To be neutral? The answer to that is, it is impossible for the church not to have a particular political opinion, but it is important that it does not blindly follow a political ideology, because if it does that, the church as an institution may not be able to challenge the ideology if it is wrong. The position of the church as the salt and light of the world should be maintained. As a body, it would be a place where everybody should feel at home and whatever the church says through the Pastor must be objective thus bringing changes to the society.

As for the involvement of the ministers of the gospel in politics, Unubi (Interview, 2025); asserts that the answer is Yes or No. According to him, yes, in the sense that the minister of the gospel is a political animal, so depriving him from politics implies doing away with his responsibility because he is a human being, a citizen of a country, and he is free to play politics according to the laws of the society.

The above is a positive involvement in the Church generally, but a minister of a congregation should not be seen siding with one party against another or even

advocating for any. If he does that, he loses his respect as a father of all and as a good shepherd following the footsteps of Christ. However, if a minister becomes partisan, such a minister must resign his appointment and go into politics, being fully aware of the changes that are in partisan politics, for example, he may be tempted to bribe, tell lies, be involved in victimisation, or criticise others. Also, whatever he does will be blown out of proportion.

Kunhiyop (2008) was of the view that the researcher, as he notes, that the Church lives in the world and therefore needs the world. If it attempts to deny this, it lapses into a position of irrelevance and insignificance in relation to the life of the world, which is incompatible with its faith in God's sovereignty and fatherly care.

In a nutshell, the above writer concluded that the church's involvement in politics is hinged on its divine role as a transformer of society for good. Anything the church does outside this is not fulfilling this divine injunction.

Challenges faced by Christians in Nigerian politics

Despite the significant involvement of Christians in Nigerian politics, the expected positive result is yet to be achieved. The non-realisation is purely due to numerous challenges being faced by Christians in our contemporary Nigerian politics. Challenges such as corruption, ethnic and religious tensions, and electoral malpractices etc pose significant challenges to the participation of Christians in Nigerian Political activities.

Osomor (2012) attests to the above as he notes that the story of Nigeria is obviously that of a failing state. He added that the socio-political realities in Nigeria are deplorable, with multifaceted problems strung from misrule. Good governance and development, according to the above author, are shadows of themselves in Nigeria. He equally asserts that democracy, which is purported to be the harbinger of good governance in some climes, is in shambles in Nigeria due to flagrant disregard for the rule of law and due process occasioned by the quest for personal or selected group advantage.

The above author averred, elections in Nigeria are marred with irregularities of varying forms and degrees in our nation state. According to him, rigging, violence and vote buying are the defining characteristics of elections in Nigeria. He added that parties in power or that have more formidable means of malpractice seek to perpetuate themselves in office or grab power by all means at the expense of the wishes of the masses.

Added to the above, Osomor further notes that politicians are countless, corrupt and overbearing. The judiciary, which ought to be the hope of the common man, has literally become an organ of the executive arm of government, such that justice swings according to the dictates the whims and caprices of those cabals in the corridors of power. He concluded that various government institutions are

catalysts and accomplices in the subversion of governance in Nigeria. The security agencies, the judiciary, government agencies such as EFCC and even some civil society organisations are willing trolls for negative governance in Nigeria. This has made the living conditions of an average Nigerian, including Christians, despicable.

The research asserts the above that in Nigeria as a nation state, while Nigerian Christians emphasise integrity as well as moral conduct, the nature of corruption and unethical behaviour in Nigerian politics rightly suggests the distinction between religious values and political activities. This, according to the researcher, undermines political trust and thus advances the effect of good governance in our nation-state.

Corruption is one of the significant challenges facing our nation-state (Nigeria) today. It is seen in several sectors, including politics, the economy, as well as everyday social interaction, leading to widespread inequality, inefficiency as well and injustice. Despite both efforts of governmental and non-governmental bodies to curb corruption, it continues unabated, thus having, advanced effect on the nation's development as well as the well-being of its citizens.

Eze in Omosor (2013), opines that the greatest problem of leadership and governance in Nigeria is the virus of corruption. Corruption, according to him, has become so rampant and prevalent that it has become a norm in society. It becomes difficult to adequately capture the dimension and extent of corruption in Nigeria. He also notes that corruption is inextricably associated with materialism. Materialism drives individuals into the way of inordinate ambition to acquire massive wealth. Today, prestige, fame and recognition are predicated upon wealth. Those who direct the affairs of society are those who have amassed wealth by any means. He further asserts that political leadership is no longer by integrity but a function of affluence. This is why notorious criminals dominate the political domain, and even at the level of community leadership.

The above author concludes that today in our nation state, political thugs, hooligans, murderers, thieves and all sorts of morally debased and demented persons grab power and perpetuate themselves in the seat of governance. What we have is a jungle kind of leadership where people including Christian politicians are harassed in various forms, looting of the public treasury, orchestration of violence, poverty entrenchment, outbreak of diseases due to mal nutrition and unhealthy environment, death toll rises in alarming rate, quality education aborted and justice is manipulated in the law court leaving developmental prospects a shadow of reality.

The researcher was also of the same view as the above writer, as he asserts that corruption in Nigerian politics is a thing of concern that hurts several aspects of society. The researcher added that corruption manifests itself in areas of bribery,

embezzlement, nepotism, as well as electoral fraud. All efforts by Christian politicians to address the above issues, with the aid of moral, ethical and theological principles to curb corruption in Nigerian politics, proved abortive.

The researcher concluded that, notwithstanding the above, despite the tireless efforts of Christian politicians to bring in sanity, there is a notable deficiency in structural, ethical and leadership training for Christian politicians. This gap, according to him, contributes to the recurrence of the so-called unethical behaviour and lack of accountability, which affects the goal of good government in our nation-state. In short, many Christian communities, according to the researcher, lack adequate civic education, which impedes their political participation as well as political awareness among the electorate. This harms policy-making processes as well as the proper accountability of elected political officials.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, from time immemorial to date, it has been discovered that greater majority of the Nigeria Christians with integrity, looked at the involvement of the church in politics as dirty game, worldly as well as ungodly. The above assertion is not true in the sense that Christian participation in politics in our nation state (Nigeria) would positively contribute to good governance in areas of ethical challenges, promotion of civic engagement, justice, equity, and the common good of the Nigerian citizens.

Politics is a pervasive part of society, affecting individuals and groups, as well as areas like religion, economy, technology and science. Nobody can claim that politics is irrelevant to their lives. The church in Nigerian society has now recognised the need to actively participate in politics and seek to have an impact on education, economics, and culture. When the church, co-operatively and individually, has an impact on a nation in these practical areas, the entire political terrain is affected, and Christian values permeate the nation (Kunhiyop, 2008).

In a nutshell, the church's involvement in politics is hinged on its divine role as a transformer of society for good. Anything the church does outside this is not fulfilling this divine injunction.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The work concludes by making the following recommendations, such as ethical training for Nigerian Christian politicians, promotion of interfaith dialogue, fostering civic education, strengthening accountability mechanisms, as well as encouraging their members to form political parties and actively participate in them.

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